

Phantom Vibrotactile Sensations on the Plantar Surface: A Wearable Insole Pilot Study

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Abstract. Vibrotactile feedback at the foot sole is investigated for rehabilitation, pedestrian navigation, and virtual ground rendering. The spatial resolution of such displays is bounded by the number of physical actuators. Phantom sensations increase the perceived resolution by rendering virtual stimuli between neighboring actuators, yet their use on the plantar surface is largely unexplored. We present a wearable vibrotactile insole with eight linear resonant actuators and report preliminary results from the first 8 participants of an ongoing localization study comparing real and phantom stimuli under static (standing) and dynamic (walking) conditions. Reported errors are medians with their interquartile range (IQR). In the static condition, phantom stimuli show descriptively larger median errors than real actuators (34.7 mm, IQR 26.8 to 40.2 vs 20.3 mm, IQR 19.8 to 26.2). During walking the gap closes, with phantom errors remaining stable (33.4 mm, IQR 26.1 to 38.9) while real errors increase to 32.8 mm (IQR 24.3 to 40.9). Phantom errors remain comparable to real-actuator errors across both conditions, suggesting that phantom sensations transfer to the plantar surface and can increase the resolution of wearable foot-sole displays.

Keywords: Vibrotactile feedback · Phantom sensation · Tactile illusion · Wearable haptics · Plantar stimulation

1 Introduction

The plantar surface mediates postural control and locomotion [6], motivating vibrotactile foot-sole feedback for rehabilitation, pedestrian navigation, and virtual ground rendering [3,9,10,2,11]. The spatial resolution of such displays scales with the number of physical actuators, yet denser arrays increase complexity, power consumption, and integration effort in wearable footwear.

Phantom sensations resolve this trade-off perceptually. Two neighboring actuators driven simultaneously with modulated amplitudes elicit a single virtual stimulus between them, which increases the perceived resolution without additional hardware [1,4]. The effect has been characterized on the forearm [4], torso [5], and wrist [7], but the plantar surface has received little attention despite its distinct mechanoreceptor density, skin mechanics, and load-bearing function. Prior work from our group characterized vibrotactile perceivability and localization on the foot sole [8] but did not address tactile illusions.

Fig. 1. Phantom sensations are perceivable on the plantar surface and localized with accuracy close to that of real actuators. (a) Wearable insole with eight physical actuators (solid, 0–7) and six phantom positions (dashed, P) rendered by the energy model [4]; the complete system is worn during treadmill walking with GUI-based response collection. (b) Perceived locations in the static condition cluster between the contributing real actuators for every phantom position, confirming the intended virtual percept. Colored dots are individual responses, ellipses are Gaussian fits, filled markers are cluster centers. (c) Per-participant median localization error by condition and stimulus type ($N = 8$, pilot subset). Phantom stimuli show descriptively larger errors than real actuators in the static condition, while during walking both distributions take a similar shape.

We investigate whether phantom sensations are perceivable on the plantar surface and how locomotion affects their localization. We present a wearable vibrotactile insole with eight linear resonant actuators and report preliminary results from the first $N = 8$ participants of an ongoing localization study under static (standing) and dynamic (walking) conditions.

2 Methods

2.1 Wearable Vibrotactile Insole

The 3D-printed thermoplastic polyurethane insole integrates eight coin-type linear resonant actuators (Vybronic VG1030001XH, 10 mm diameter, $f_0 \approx 210$ Hz) and eight force-sensing resistors (Ohmite FSR06) in modular press-fit housings (Fig. 1a). A control unit worn on the lower leg drives the actuators through DRV2605L drivers controlled by an ESP32 microcontroller and communicates wirelessly with a host PC via WiFi and UDP.

2.2 User Study

Six phantom positions are placed between neighboring actuator pairs and rendered with the energy-based model [1,4] (Fig. 1a). Five are one-dimensional phantoms between two actuators along a line; one is a two-dimensional phantom rendered between four actuators forming a rectangle. This paper reports descriptive results from the first eight participants of an ongoing study (23.8 ± 1.8 years; 4 M, 4 F). Each participant localized 15 stimulus types (8 real, 6 phantom,

1 dummy), presented three times per condition. The static condition was performed standing. The dynamic condition was performed during treadmill walking at self-selected speed with stimuli triggered on heel strike. Each stimulus consisted of three 400 ms pulses at the actuator resonance frequency. Participants reported the perceived location on a GUI foot outline and rated intensity on a visual analog scale (0–100). Noise-canceling headphones with pink noise masked auditory cues. The study received a positive vote from the Ethics Committee of Technische Universität Darmstadt (EK 11/2026). Formal statistical analysis is planned for the full cohort.

3 Preliminary Results

Per-participant median localization errors with their interquartile range (IQR) are 20.3 mm (IQR 19.8 to 26.2) for real and 34.7 mm (IQR 26.8 to 40.2) for phantom stimuli in the static condition, and 32.8 mm (IQR 24.3 to 40.9) and 33.4 mm (IQR 26.1 to 38.9) respectively during walking (Fig. 1c). In the static condition, phantom stimuli show descriptively larger errors than real actuators, while the two distributions overlap closely during walking. Across conditions, phantom errors remain comparable, whereas real-actuator errors increase descriptively with locomotion. Localization performance also varies across anatomical regions (Fig. 1b). Medial-forefoot phantoms reach errors comparable to their contributing real actuators, while the 2D phantom in the midfoot shows the largest error and dispersion, consistent with the lower mechanoreceptor density of this region. A Friedman test on the four cells does not reach significance with this pilot sample ($\chi^2(3) = 4.95$, $p = 0.18$). Formal testing is deferred to the full dataset.

4 Open Research Questions and Interdisciplinary Exchange

Phantom sensations appear perceivable on the plantar surface, with preliminary data suggesting stable performance during walking while real-actuator errors increase. If confirmed in the full dataset, this locomotion-robustness motivates several open questions for which we seek collaboration. Phantoms were descriptively less accurate than real actuators in the static condition, particularly at the 2D midfoot. Per-actuator detection thresholds may guide individualized amplitude adjustment to close this gap. Gait-phase plantar pressure may drive load-adaptive rendering that exploits the observed locomotion-robustness. Input from psychophysics, perceptual modeling, and biomechanics would advance these directions.

Phantom acuity varies with anatomical region, highest in the medial forefoot and lowest at the 2D midfoot. Applications can place fine-grained cues at high-acuity regions and coarse alerts elsewhere, for instance in VR ground-texture rendering, navigation, or gait rehabilitation. Perspectives from VR/HCI, rehabilitation engineering, and clinical gait analysis would inform these applications.

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